

Chemical Reactions in Infra-red Radiations (7304 Å).

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Very few chemical reactions have been investigated in presence of infra-red radiations, and the majority of photochemical changes studied are under the influence of radiations of short wave-lengths.

In these laboratories (compare Bhattacharya and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, **175**, 357; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 148) we have investigated the kinetics, temperature coefficients and quantum efficiency of several chemical reactions under the influence of radiation of mean wave-length 7304 Å. In this communication we are recording our results and conclusions on the velocity of chemical reactions in infra-red radiation.

The kinetics of the reactions have been determined in the dark and in radiation of wave-length 7304 Å at different temperatures and the quantum efficiency has been measured in the same region. The source of light was a 1000 Watt gas-filled tungsten filament lamp operated at 4.6 amperes. The lamp was placed in a box and an electric radiator was worked at the back of the lamp in order to keep it cool. Two big lenses were placed between the light source to obtain parallel light. To isolate different wave-lengths of spectral region a set of gelatin film filters (Wallace M and S) were used. The radiomicrometer was placed at a distance of one metre from the light source. Water at a constant temperature from a thermostat was circulated round the reaction vessel, which is a silica cube.

The changes in the reactions studied were determined either by suitable titrations or spectrophotometric measurements.

The following are the experimental results.

Bleaching of M/7176-neocyanin by Air at 40°.

Time in minutes	...	0	50	92	135	185	
Extinction coefficient	...	0.70	0.61	0.54	0.48	0.42	
k_1 (Monomolecular)	...	—	0.00119	0.00122	0.00121	0.00119	Mean 0.0012

Other results are summarised in the following tables, where

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a_0}{a_0 - x} \quad (\text{Monomolecular});$$

$$k_{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{2}{t} \left[a_{\frac{1}{2}} - (a - x)_{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (\text{Semimolecular});$$

$$k_0 = \frac{x}{t} \quad (\text{Zeromolecular}).$$

In some of the reactions involving iodine as one of the reactants, the order of the light reaction is semimolecular whilst in the dark it is unimolecular. In these cases, in order to get comparable values, the dark reaction velocities have also been calculated according to the semimolecular formula.

Results.

Region: $-\lambda = 7608\text{\AA} - 7000\text{\AA}$; $\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$ (Mean).

Temperature.	Velocity of reaction in $\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$.	Velocity of reaction in the dark.	Temp. coeff. of the dark reaction.	Temp. coeff. of the reaction in light $(\lambda = 7304\text{\AA})$ after deducting the dark reaction.	Quantum efficiency.
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Bleaching of M/7176-neocyanin by air.

	k_{λ}	k_1			
20°	0·00102				1·1
30°	0·00114	Negligible.	—	1·12	2·1
40°	0·00120			1·05	3·1

Bleaching of M/24166-dicyanin.

25°	0·00309	0·00099			0·29
30°	0·00340	0·00127			0·66
			1·354	1·056	
40°	0·00397	0·00172			0·89

6·75N-Citric acid and N/44·4-chromic acid, 10 c.c. each.

24°	0·000487	0·000359			1·5
			3·73	2·89	
34°	0·00171	0·00134			4·2
			3·65	2·75	
44°	0·00587	0·00485			5·2

Temperature.	Velocity of reaction in $\lambda = 7304 \text{ \AA}$.	Velocity of reaction in the dark.	Temp. coeff. of the dark reaction.	Temp. coeff. of the reaction in light ($\lambda = 7304 \text{ \AA}$) after deducting the dark reaction.	Quantum efficiency.
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N/4.72-Lactic acid and N/44.4-chromic acid, 10 c.c. each.

	k_1	k_1			
22°	0.00120	0.00108			1.8
			1.8	1.75	
32°	0.00216	0.00195			3.2
			1.75	1.70	
42°	0.00377	0.00341			4.6

N/4.27-Tartaric acid and N/44.4-chromic acid, 10 c.c. each.

22°	0.00154	0.00143			5.6
			2.13	2	
32°	0.00327	0.00305			8.3
			2.04	1.95	
42°	0.00664	0.00621			11.0

N/5-Oxalic acid and N/111-chromic acid, 10 c.c. each.

20°	0.00335	0.00273			2.6
			1.9	1.76	
30°	0.00627	0.00518			4.1
			1.61	1.67	
40°	0.0112	0.00938			5.0

*N/19.47-Oxalic acid and N/421.3-chromic acid
+ N/337-MnSO₄ + N/2.78-H₂SO₄.*

	k_0	k_0			
21°	0.195	0.147			3
			2.94	1.42	
31°	0.504	0.434			9.5

Temperature.	Velocity of reaction in $\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}$.	Velocity of reaction in the dark.	Temp. coeff. of the dark reaction.	Temp. coeff. of the reaction in light \circ ($\lambda = 7804\text{\AA}$) after deducting the dark reaction.	Quantum efficiency.
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N/89-Quinine sulphate in N/2-H₂SO₄ and N/80.88-chromic acid in 1.31N-H₂SO₄.

	k_1	k_1	$k_{25}^\circ/k_{25}^\circ$		
25°	0.000232	0.000204			2.3
30°	0.000295	0.000262	1.6	1.4	0.45
35°	0.000365	0.000326			2.58

N/4.69-Sodium lactate and N/100-iodine, 10 c.c. each.

20°	0.000797	0.000720			3.97
			2.49	2.21	
30°	0.00196	0.00179			6.52
			2.31	2.06	
40°	0.00449	0.00414			8.38

N/5.12-Sodium malonate and N/100-iodine, 10 c.c. each.

20°	0.00287	0.00227			9.8
			2.21	2	
30°	0.00623	0.00503			1.24
			2.16	1.92	
40°	0.0132	0.0109			13.6

N/2.42-Sodium tartrate and N/100-iodine, 10 c.c. each.

20°	0.000451	0.000378			4.2
			2.51	2.26	
30°	0.00118	0.000948			7.1
			2.49	2.18	
40°	0.00272	0.00236			9.6

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Temperature. Velocity of reaction in $\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$. Velocity of reaction in the dark. Temp. coeff. of the dark reaction. Temp. coeff. of the reaction in light ($\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$) after deducting the dark reaction. Quantum efficiency.

N/8-Sodium malate and N/125-iodine, 10 c.c. each.

	$k_{\frac{1}{2}}$	k_1			
30°	0.00417	0.000949			15
			1.61	1.57	
40°	0.00612	0.00153			5.6

N/5.76 Sodium citrate and N/100-iodine, 10 c.c. each.

23°	0.00831	0.00115	1.63	1.63	2.6
33°	0.0148	0.00188			11.2

N/7.17-Sodium formate and N/111.4-iodine and N/4.44-sodium acetate.

20°	0.0132	0.0097			54
			4.3	4.0	
30°	0.0357	0.0417			110

N/10.25-Potassium oxalate and N/113.6-iodine.

				$k_{30^\circ}/k_{20^\circ}$	
20°	0.00368				3.7
30°	0.0131	Negligible.	—	3.56	7.5
36°	0.0256				74

N/6.06-Ferrous sulphate and N/90.92-iodine and N/3-H₂SO₄.

			$k_{34.5^\circ}/k_{24.5^\circ}$		
24.5°	0.00358	0.000373			8.34
			2.92	2.85	
30°	0.00903	0.000675			14.2
34.5°	0.0128	0.00110			52.7

N/1.5-Sodium nitrite and N/32-iodine and N/6-CH₃·COONa.

			$k_{30^\circ}/k_{25^\circ}$		
20°	0.00772	0.000353			32
			2.71	2.61	
25°	0.0136	0.000574			66
30°	0.0220	0.000955			77

Temperature.	Velocity of reaction in $\lambda=7304\text{\AA}$.	Velocity of reaction in the dark.	Temp. coeff. of the dark reaction.	Temp. coeff. of the reaction in light ($\lambda=7304\text{\AA}$) after deducting the dark reaction.	Quantum efficiency.
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49% -Acetone and N/50-iodine + N/9.42-HCl.

	k_0	k_0			
21°	0.0701	0.0650	3.21	2.94	3.6
31°	0.224	0.209	3.0	2.87	11.2
41°	0.672	0.629			23.8

43% -Methyl alcohol and N/101.7-bromine, 10 c.c. each.

	k_1	k_1			
20°	0.00453	0.00325	2.5	2.42	3.65
30°	0.0111	0.0080	2.45	2.32	6.8
40°	0.0269	0.0196			16.7

25% -Ethyl alcohol and N/113.7-bromine, 10 c.c. each.

20°	0.00540	0.00465			1.1
30°	0.0152	0.0132	2.84	2.67	2.1
40°	0.0416	0.0366	2.77	2.45	3.5

N/12.23-Rochelle salt and N/121-bromine + N/6.6-CH₃.COONa.

			$k_{30}^{\circ}/k_{20}^{\circ}$		
20°	0.0133	0.00372			24.4
25°	0.0242	0.00674	3.28	2.08	26
30°	0.0821	0.0123			69

N/250-Ferric chloride and N/50-NH₄CNS, 10 c.c. each.

20°	0.000284			2.5	3.4
30°	0.000709	Negligible.	—	2.3	4.6
40°	0.00163				7.3

N/50-Potassium persulphate and N/5-KI.

20°	0.00995	0.00758			5
30°	0.0183	0.0144	1.90	1.64	13.4
40°	0.0332	0.0270	1.87	1.60	28.6

Temperature.	Velocity of reaction in $\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$.	Velocity of reaction in the dark.	Temp. coeff. of the dark reaction.	Temp. coeff. of the reaction in light \circ ($\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$) after deducting the dark reaction.	Quantum efficiency.
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Decomposition of M/80.8-sodium cobaltinitrite.

	k_1	k_1			
20°	0.000804	0.000589	3.5	2.7	1.1
30°	0.00266	0.00208	3.04	2.6	2.5
40°	0.00783	0.00632			6

0.898N-Sodium formate and N/15-HgCl₂.

20°	0.000808	0.000665	4.36	4.12	27.3
30°	0.00349	0.00230			68

N/19.12-Oxalic acid and N/421.3-KMnO₄ and N/337-MnSO₄ + N/2.78-H₂SO₄.

8.5°	0.0351	0.0220		$k_{24.5} / k_{14.5}$	39
14.5°	0.0652	0.0466	3.09	2.4	36
24.5°	0.1696	0.144			36

N/4.72-Lactic acid (10 c.c.) + N/86.25-KMnO₄ (5 c.c.) + N/69-MnSO₄ (5 c.c.).

19°	0.0196	0.0149	2.5	2.3	14
29°	0.0481	0.0373	2.48	2.08	23
39°	0.115	0.925			41

N/5.36-Tartaric acid (10 c.c.) + N/98.45-KMnO₄ (5 c.c.) + N/69-MnSO₄ (5 c.c.).

16°	0.0188	0.0140	2.46	2.3	11
26°	0.0455	0.0345	2.40	2.2	26
36°	0.107	0.0828			37

Temperature.	Velocity of reaction in $\lambda = 7304\text{A}.$	Velocity of reaction in the dark.	Temp. coeff. of the dark reaction.	Temp. coeff. of the reaction in light \circ ($\lambda = 7304\text{A}$) after deducting the dark reaction.	Quantum efficiency
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N/5-Citric acid (10 c.c.) + *N/50-KMnO₄* (5 c.c.)
+ *M/89-MnSO₄* (5 c.c.).

	k_1	k_2			
15°	0·00609	0·00473			9
25°	0·0170	0·0138	2·92	2·35	17
30°	0·0255	0·0219			28

N/10-Potassium oxalate + *N/100-bromine* (2 gms. KBr in 100 c.c. of *N/100-Br₂*).

20°	0·0248	0·00456	5·61	3·06	36
30°	0·0618	0·0256	5·20	3·0	62
40°	0·220	0·133			85

The foregoing results show that several chemical reactions are appreciably accelerated by radiations of wave-length 7304A° which lies in the infra-red region. We have carefully measured the extinction coefficient of the reacting substances by Nutting's spectrophotometer and have found appreciable absorption in the region $\lambda = 7000\text{A}^\circ$. It is apparent therefore that the reacting substances actually absorb the radiation of wave-length 7304A° and are activated by the absorption of energy and then react chemically. We have also observed that all these reactions can be accelerated by radiations of wave-lengths 5650A° and 4725A° and these wave-lengths are appreciably absorbed by the reacting systems. We have measured the kinetics, temperature coefficients and quantum efficiency of several reactions in these regions as well (*cf.* Bhattacharya and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 175, 357; 1928, 176, 372).

The extinction coefficient of neocyanin shows that the radiations of wave-lengths longer than 5670A° are completely absorbed even by very dilute solutions of neocyanin (*vide* next Table). As the wave-length of the incident radiation is decreased the absorption passes

through a minimum and then increases with the decrease of wave-length. The velocity of the bleaching of neocyanin is greatest in the region $\lambda=7804 \text{ \AA}^\circ$, less in the region $\lambda=5650 \text{ \AA}^\circ$ and least in the region $\lambda=4725 \text{ \AA}^\circ$. This shows that the velocity of reaction and absorption go hand in hand.

We have measured photographically the absorption of several of these reacting mixtures using a Hilger quartz-spectrograph with a copper arc as a source of light. With an exposure of about 2 minutes no absorption is observed with mixtures of chromic acid and organic acids in the region of wave-lengths greater than 4725 \AA° using panchromatic plate but our experimental results on the velocity measurements show that these reactions are not only accelerated by radiations of wave-length 4725 \AA° and 5650 \AA° which lie in the visible part of the spectrum but even by radiation of $\lambda=7804 \text{ \AA}^\circ$, which lies in the infra-red region. It appears therefore that small amount of absorption of incident light cannot be observed by a photographic method on short exposure. We have measured the extinction coefficients of an aqueous solution of neocyanin and mixtures of citric acid and chromic acid and the following results have been obtained.

Wave-length.	Extinction coefficient of an aqueous solution of neocyanin.	Extinction coefficient of citric acid and chromic acid.
7000 \AA°	Complete absorption	0.04
6707	„	0.11
5970	Beyond scale	0.13
5670	1.96	0.16
5490	0.86	0.18
5320	0.44	0.22
5200	0.21	0.38
5000	0.24	0.52
4910	0.27	0.53
4800	0.31	0.60
4720	0.43	0.65
4670	0.48	0.91
4550	0.54	0.98
4400	0.62	1.11

Hence the extinction coefficient measurements show that all radiations from 7000 \AA to 4400 \AA are actually absorbed by an aqueous solution of neocyanin and the mixture of citric acid and chromic acid. Similar results showing appreciable absorption of all radiations from 7000 to 4400 \AA have been observed with the other reacting systems.

It is well-known that the absorption of radiation by molecules is a very complex phenomenon. A very thin layer of mercury vapour shows marked absorption of wave-length 2537 \AA whilst columns of air 9.5 and 39.4 metres long respectively show feeble absorption of radiations 7600 and 6900 \AA . These absorptions are ascribed to oxygen of the atmosphere (compare Foote and Moher, "Origin of Spectra", 1922, p. 89; King, *Astrophys. J.*, 1922, **55**, 411). The few exceptions of Stokes' law of fluorescence where the frequency of emitted light is greater than the frequency of the incident radiation observed by Wood (*Phil. Mag.*, 1928, (vii), **6**, 310) and others with vapours of sodium, iodine and other fluorescent substances have been explained from the following point of view. In a system there are few molecules the energy of which is much greater than the energy of the average molecules. When the incident radiations falls on such an active molecule, the molecule is further activated by the absorption of incident radiation and under favourable conditions it can revert directly to the inactive state giving out radiation of greater energy content than that available from the incident radiation. Recently Raman (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1928, **2**, 399) has observed this phenomenon (anti-Stokes effect) with substances such as carbon tetrachloride and benzene when illuminated by radiation of wave-length 4304 \AA which is not supposed to be absorbed but scattered by molecules of carbon tetrachloride or benzene. It is apparent therefore that there can be activating of molecules and a shift towards the shorter wave-length side even with so called scattered radiations.

Incidentally it should be mentioned that this phenomenon of shift wave-length is a measure of the number of active molecules present in a system.

After having accelerated several photochemical reaction by radiations of wave-lengths 4725 \AA , 5650 \AA and 7304 \AA , we are definitely of the opinion that all these radiations are appreciably absorbed by the reacting substances and this we have been able to prove by the measurements of extinction coefficients, though photographically no absorption is observed.

According to the radiation hypothesis of Trautz (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1906, 4, 160), Perrin (*Ann. Physik*, 1919, 11, 1) and Lewis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 2330 ; 1915, 107, 233) we can easily calculate from the temperature coefficient of the thermal reaction the wave-length of the radiation which should accelerate the chemical change. The following results have been obtained :

Reaction.	Temp. coefficient (dark).	Wave-length.
Decomposition of sodium-cobaltinitrite	3.5	1.3 μ
Acetone and iodine in presence of HCl	3.21	1.38 μ
Rochelle salt and bromine	3.2	..
Sodium formate and mercuric chloride	4.36	1.08 μ
Potassium oxalate and iodine	7.2	0.86 μ
Potassium oxalate and bromine	5.6	0.94 μ
Sodium formate and iodine	4.3	1.09 μ
Ferrous sulphate and iodine	2.92	1.46 μ
Citric acid and chromic acid	3.73	1.2 μ
Oxalic acid, chromic acid and manganous sulphate.	2.94	1.44 μ

It is evident, therefore, that all the reactions should be accelerated by short infra-red radiation. As a matter of fact, we have observed accelerations in all the reactions investigated by us by radiation of wave-length 7304A°. We are of the opinion that the wave-lengths obtained by calculation from the thermal temperature coefficients may be regarded as the threshold limit. No acceleration of the change is possible with radiations of longer wave-lengths than the threshold limit. This point may also be made clear from another line of argument. Following Arrhenius, we know that there are active and inactive molecules in a system and that chemical changes take place between the active molecules only and it has also been

held that an increase in temperature means an increase in the number of active molecules. Now those dark reactions, which are very sensitive to the influence of temperature, are evidently the ones where the difference in energy between the active and inactive molecules is very marked. In other words, in activating the inactive molecules in such a system absorption of energy in quanta of greater energy content would be necessary than in a system where the difference in energy levels between the active and inactive molecules is not so prominent.

Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707) has shown that fast dark reactions have smaller temperature coefficients than comparatively slow ones. This is because in a fast reaction the number of active molecules is much greater than in the slower ones. Hence a fast reaction would not be so sensitive to the influence of temperature. Thus it appears that those reactions which have small temperature coefficients in the dark could be activated by quanta of smaller energy content and consequently such reactions should be accelerated by short infra-red radiations. On the other hand, those thermal reactions which are very sensitive to the influence of temperature should be activated by radiations of larger energy quanta and hence ought to be sensitive to shorter wave-lengths.

It must be pointed out clearly that according to the views advanced in the foregoing pages we can get the threshold frequencies from the measurements of temperature coefficients of the dark reactions. Radiations of longer wave-lengths will not promote the reaction in question. The main difference between this conception and the Perrin-Lewis radiation hypothesis is that according to the latter view the wave-length calculated from the temperature coefficient should bring about the maximum speed of that reaction in question whilst according to the conception now put forward, the threshold frequency is the minimum frequency necessary for the carrying out of the reaction.

The foregoing conclusion is corroborated by the observation of Taylor and co-workers (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 31, 38) that the active frequencies for the combination of hydrogen and chlorine are not confined to any restricted regions, since, when light is filtered through chlorine, its photochemical effect falls rapidly not towards zero but towards a definite residual value. Thus some of the very feebly absorbed frequency must be active in the combination of hydrogen and chlorine.

From the foregoing experimental results and conclusions it will be clear that the main argument raised by Langmuir (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 2090), Polanyi (*Z. Physik*, 1920, **1**, 337; 1920, **2**, 90) and others against the radiation hypothesis of chemical change that reacting substances do not show absorption of such radiation as are obtained from the temperature coefficient of the thermal reaction seems doubtful.

Summary.

(1) The following reactions have been accelerated by radiation of wave-length 7304 Å°:—(i) bleaching of neocyanin, (ii) bleaching of dicyanin; (iii) citric acid and chromic acid; (iv) lactic acid and chromic acid; (v) tartaric acid and chromic acid; (vi) oxalic acid and chromic acid; (vii) oxalic acid and chromic acid and manganous sulphate; (viii) quinine sulphate and chromic acid; (ix) sodium lactate and iodine; (x) sodium malonate and iodine; (xi) sodium tartrate and iodine; (xii) sodium malate and iodine; (xiii) sodium citrate and iodine; (xiv) sodium formate and iodine; (xv) potassium oxalate and iodine; (xvi) ferrous sulphate and iodine; (xvii) sodium nitrite and iodine; (xviii) acetone and iodine; (xix) methyl alcohol and bromine; (xx) ethyl alcohol and bromine; (xxi) Rochelle salt and bromine; (xxii) ferric chloride and ammonium thiocyanate; (xxiii) potassium persulphate and potassium iodide; (xxiv) decomposition of sodium cobaltinitrite; (xxv) sodium formate and mercuric chloride; (xxvi) oxalic acid and potassium permanganate and manganous sulphate; (xxvii) lactic acid and potassium permanganate and manganous sulphate; (xxviii) tartaric acid and potassium permanganate and manganous sulphate; (xxix) citric acid and potassium permanganate and manganous sulphate; (xxx) potassium oxalate and bromine.

(2) The temperature coefficients of all these reactions in radiation of wave-length 7304 Å° are less than those of the corresponding dark reactions. Hence radiation of wave-length 7304 Å° accelerates the above reactions and produces a lowering of their temperature coefficients.

(3) The quantum efficiency of all these reactions usually increases with increasing temperature.

(4) Measurements of extinction coefficients show that all radiations of wave-length from 4400 Å° to 7000 Å° are absorbed by the

above reacting systems and thus they are accelerated by the absorption of the incident radiation.

(5) The wave-lengths obtained by calculation from the thermal temperature coefficients may be regarded as the threshold limit. No appreciable acceleration of the chemical change is possible with radiations of longer wave-lengths than the threshold limit. All radiations of frequency greater than the threshold frequency are appreciably absorbed by the reacting substances and can accelerate the reactions investigated.

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